

control treatments, pretilachlor plus (0.3 kg ai ha⁻¹) with one hand weeding significantly reduced total weed dry weight at 60 DAS, with a maximum

WCE of 85%. This treatment also produced the best yield—5.49 t ha⁻¹ (see table). Thiobencarb (1.5 kg ai ha⁻¹) with one hand weeding was as effective as

two hand weedings. No post-emergence herbicide was as effective for dry-seeded lowland rice. ■

Research methodology

The relationship between experimental plot research and Texas rice producers' ratoon field results

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At several recent Texas (USA) rice industry meetings, rice consultants and producers mentioned observing input responses different from those reported by extension and research specialists. This study documents the correlation between scientists' recommendations based on existing theory drawn from rice plot research and actual results from commercial fields obtained from producers' surveys during 1987-89. Scientists' expert ex ante opinions on the effects of several predetermined, decision, and uncertain factors on ratoon crop rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) field yield and quality (milling yield, head yield, and grade) were documented. A modified Delphi procedure, whereby scientists come to a consensus agreement, was used to determine an extensive set of independent variables hypothesized to either positively or negatively affect ratoon crop yield and quality. The scientists' identified variables provided the basis for a mail survey of Texas rice producers' cultural practices and yield-quality responses

Summary statistics for the ratoon crop models, 1987-89 Texas ratoon crop survey.

Item	Ratoon crop models ^a			
	RY ^b	RYM ^c	RHY ^d	RG ^e
F value	9.8350	2.6570	2.5010	1.6730
Prob > F	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0047
R square	0.6397	0.3413	0.4057	0.0203
Adj R square	0.5746	0.2129	0.2898	0.0816
CV	1.6388	2.6347	5.2959	71.1072
Observations (no.)	413	381	381	380

^aEach model has approximately 40-50 variables that were hypothesized to affect yield and quality according to rice research and extension scientists. The variables include those that are (a) known at the beginning of the production period (predetermined variables such as soil type), (b) controlled by the decision maker within the production period (decision variables (such as fertilizer management), and (c) beyond the decision maker's control (uncertain variables, such as climate). ^bRY = ratoon crop yield. ^cRYM = ratoon crop milling yield. ^dRHY = ratoon crop head yield. ^eRG = ratoon crop grade.

during 1987-89. Following collection of the survey data, multiple regression procedures and associated statistical tests were used to identify statistically significant ratoon yield and quality-influencing variables.

Table presents summary regression results. The predetermined variables included management (3 variables), soils (2), water management (2), land preparation (4), and rotation (7). The decision variables were varieties (2), fertilization (10), emergence / seeding (3), water management (8), diseases (3), pests (4), and harvesting (10). The uncertainty variables consisted of weather (6) and diseases (2).

Low coefficients of determination indicate that the model formulations and the hypotheses identified for the ratoon crop yield and quality models do not fully account for the variability in actual ratoon crop field yields and quality. In many cases, scientists' hypotheses matched producers' ratoon yield and quality responses; however, sometimes the apparent direction of effect in

the data set was in an opposite direction than hypothesized. For example, 1988 was hypothesized to have been a more favorable year for ratoon field yields and quality. Statistical results indicate that the scientists' hypothesis of higher field yields was supported, but their hypothesis regarding higher quality (milling yield) was rejected.

Comparison of the number of statistically significant variables between the yield and quality models indicates that 42% of the scientists' hypothesized yield variables were significant, whereas 45% of the scientists' hypothesized quality variables were significant. Hypothesized signs for the statistically significant variables were then compared with calculated signs for alternative farm scenarios based on the regression results. Agreement with scientists' hypotheses occurs if the calculated sign is the same as the hypothesized sign. Such "in agreement" results suggest that scientists well recognize and understand the effect of these factors on Texas rice farmers' ratoon crop yields and quality. Comparison between the yield and quality models indicates that, for the yield model, 36% of the statistically significant hypotheses were in agreement, whereas 24% were in agreement for the quality models. In summary, scientists were less likely to determine the input impacts on quality rather than yield. These results indicate the importance of determining direct and interactive effects of production variables on rice quality.

The use of producer surveys provides opportunities for researchers to extensively evaluate numerous producer circumstances beyond the capability of experimental plot research and verification trials. This type of evalua-

tion can lead to the identification of interaction variables and constraints to production. In instances where new production practices evolve (such as the introduction of high-yielding semidwarf rice varieties), producer surveys may point to the need for a refinement of recommendations.

Producers can use the results to compare their farm responses with those of others. Identification of the principal sources of variation will allow producers to focus on information that can provide a basis for refining their production practices. Producers' knowledge of the relationship between

production inputs and rice quality can be improved if research and extension specialists report yield and quality results from research and experimental trials and if more research is devoted to producer-controlled impacts such as postharvest handling. ■

Comparing methods of stability analysis in rice hybrids

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Yield heterosis in rice is reported to interact with environment. Identifying rice hybrids with stable performance is a prerequisite to successfully exploiting this technology over a large area. The popular parameter for selection of stable entries used by many breeders is the varietal mean averaged over locations. Another method is to rank entries for each location and then use mean performance of the rank to assess their potential. It is well known that genotype \times environment ($G \times E$) interactions

in multilocal yield trials and the comparison of cultivar means are not very useful. In addition, the mean and its ranks do not indicate the location-wise magnitude of differences between the test entry and the standard check against which selection is to be made. In recent years, many new methods have been proposed for stability analysis. We compared the following three methods with selection based on the experimental mean: 1) a superiority measure of a cultivar, 2) nonparametric measures of phenotypic stability, and 3) relative yield as a measure.

We used the grain yield data of a hybrid rice trial conducted over 12 locations in the 1994 wet season for the study, and calculated the rank correlation (r_s) between methods. The results showed that selection based on means

of entries was closer to method 3, $r_s = 0.99$, followed by the superiority measure ($r_s = 0.95$). The ranking based on nonparametric measure was not related to the mean. Of the three methods used, the superiority measure was found to be useful for identifying stable hybrids. We analyzed the yield data from six trials conducted during 1994-95 to ascertain the usefulness of the superiority measure for identifying stable hybrids. The best-yielding hybrid was found to be the most stable. The superiority measure—as a method—is simple, convenient, and quite useful, because it uses only one parameter, which makes comparison among test genotypes easier. This method also indicates the highest yielding genotype, one that could be recommended for the whole region. ■

Education and communication

Role of voluntary agencies in popularizing hybrid rice production in India

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The Sri Aurobindo Institute of Rural Development, Gaddipalli, a nonprofit-oriented, nonsectarian, voluntary, and autonomous organization was established in 1973. A Krishi Vigyan Kendra (KVK) was started in 1985 with

funds from the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR). This KVK was judged as the best among 261 KVKs in the country during 1994-95. Nalgonda District is in the southern Telangana zone of Andhra Pradesh. This is a rural district and 88% of the population depends on agriculture. Hybrid rice in China on a large scale proved to have a more than 25% yield advantage over conventional pureline varieties. The wide adaptability of rice hybrids has produced increased rice production and productivity in China since the mid-1980s. This success prompted ICAR to accelerate research on hybrid rice, through an ICAR-

UNDP-funded project in India. This research network project involved 12 research centers (two lead, seven associate, and three strategic centers) and state seed production agencies located in the target environment. Through this network, several rice hybrids were developed and released for commercial cultivation. To popularize hybrid rice production on a large scale, the Sri Aurobindo Institute developed an integrated project that involved adaptive research at the institute farm; on-farm testing in farmers' fields; layout demonstrations on hybrid rice seed production; production and distribution of good quality hybrid rice